

Review Paper

Microsphere Study

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ABSTRACT

Microspheres are solid, spherical drug delivery systems with particle sizes ranging from 1 to 1000 μm . They improve therapeutic efficacy by delivering controlled and targeted release. They are made from natural or synthetic polymers and can encapsulate pharmaceuticals in a polymeric matrix or a unique coating. Microspheres can assist reduce dose frequency, reduce side effects, and improve patient compliance. Depending on the physicochemical parameters of the drug and polymer, many preparation procedures are used, including single emulsion, double emulsion, solvent evaporation, phase separation coacervation, and spray drying. Microspheres are categorized into several varieties, including bioadhesive, magnetic, floating, radioactive, and polymeric microspheres, each with a distinct therapeutic purpose. These methods made considerable use of chemotherapy, gene delivery, vaccination adjuvants, ocular delivery, and lymphatic targeting.

INTRODUCTION

The definition of microspheres is solid, roughly Sphere-shaped objects with a diameter ranging from 1 to 1000 micrometers, which may be in the form of microcrystalline crystals or disseminated medicines in certain solutions. Both the words "microcapsules" and "microspheres" are frequently used interchangeably. [1]. Microspheres are sometimes referred to as microparticles. Microspheres can be made from a variety of artificial and natural materials. Glass, polymer, and ceramic microspheres are among types that are

sold commercially. The microsphere plays an important role. Reduce adverse effects and increase the absorption of conventional medications. Microspheres are spherical, freely moving particles composed of biodegradable polymers. There are two different kinds of microspheres: microcapsules and micromatrices. Microcapsules are small containers with a distinct capsule wall encircling the contents, while micromatrices are structures where the material that is imprisoned is dispersed throughout the matrix. [2] A microsphere is defined as "monolithic spheres or therapeutic substances dispersed either

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as a molecular particle dispersion or a throughout the matrix." The drug particles can be distributed at the molecular or macroscale within a framework made up of one or more miscible polymers. Polyethylene and polystyrene are the two most widely used types of polymer microspheres. Polystyrene microspheres are frequently used in biomedical applications because of their ability to streamline procedures like cell sorting and antibody precipitation.[4] Polystyrene microspheres are important for biological and medical research because proteins and ligands link to them firmly and quickly. Microencapsulation allows for customized and delayed drug release. Because of its small particle size, it is widely distributed throughout the digestive tract, enhancing drug absorption and reducing side effects. Drug production occurs at a specific location that irritates the gastrointestinal mucosa.[5]

Methods of Preparation

- Single emulsion method
- Double emulsion method
- Solvent evaporation method
- Phase separation coacervation method
- Spray drying method

Single emulsion method

Natural sources of microparticulate carriers include proteins and diet. Preparation process involves a single emulsion. Natural polymers dissolve or are spread in an aqueous media. The combination is then deposited in an oil-based, non-aqueous medium. The scattered globule is cross-linked in the next stage of processing. There are two methods for connecting materials: heat or chemical. Connecting chemicals like glutaraldehyde acid, chloride, and formaldehyde. [6]

Double emulsion method

Vaccines, peptides, proteins, and water-soluble medications are all great candidates for the double emulsion method of microsphere manufacturing. It entails creating several emulsions or a double w/o/w emulsion. This technique can be applied to both synthetic and natural polymers. A dispersion aqueous protein solution is present in the lipophilic organic continuous phase. The active ingredients may be present in this protein solution. The protein in the continuous phase is eventually wrapped by the polymer solution, which is often composed of the dispersed aqueous phase. After that, the aqueous polyvinyl alcohol solution (PVA) is mixed with the primary emulsion and either homogenized or sonicated. This leads to the creation of a twofold emulsion. Next, either solvent extraction or solvent evaporation must be used to remove the solvent from the emulsion. [7]

Solvent evaporation method

This method, which is used to produce microparticles, involves extracting the organic phase using an organic solvent. Water is a miscible organic solvent used in the procedure, and the organic phase is removed by water extraction. The process reduces the lengthening time of the microspheres. One method of the process involves adding the medication directly. Elimination is influenced by a number of variables, including the volume of the emulsion in relation to a polymer's solubility profile in water, the amount of solvent, and the water's temperature.[8]

Phase separation coacervation method

This approach aims to minimize polymer solubility during the natural phase, resulting in the formation of phase-rich polymers known as coacervates. The approach combines the drug-containing polymer solution with an incompatible polymer. The first polymer absorbs drug particles,

leading to phase separation. Polymer solidification occurs through non-solvent addition, resulting in the formation of microspheres of polylactic acid. A polymer incompatible with butadiene is utilized. The rate of coacervate production affects polymer dispersion, particle size, and agglomeration. Therefore, the process variables are crucial. To prevent agglomeration, rapidly swirl suspended materials with a stirrer at the appropriate speed. The production of microspheres results in polymerized globules. [7]

Spray drying method

It is a closed, one-step system method that works with many materials, including heat-sensitive ones. Both the polymer covering and the medicine are suspended. Additionally, it can dissolve or be suspended in an emulsion or coacervate system. The drug and polymer are dissolved using methylene chloride. For example, polylactide microspheres can be formed in the polymer solution or dissolved in an appropriate solvent (aqueous or not). The size of the microspheres is influenced by the spraying speed, drug solution based on polymer supply rate, nozzle size, temperature in the drying and gathering chambers, and dimensions within the two chambers. [9]

TYPES OF MICROSPHERES

1. Bioadhesive microspheres

Adhesion can be defined as sticking of drug to the membrane by using the sticking property of the water soluble polymers. Adhesion of drug delivery device to the mucosal membrane such as buccal, ocular, rectal, nasal etc can be termed as bioadhesion. These kinds of microspheres exhibit a prolonged residence time at the site of application and causes intimate contact with the absorption site and produces better therapeutic action. [10]

2. Magnetic microspheres

This kind of delivery system is very much important which localizes the drug to the disease site. In this larger amount of freely circulating drug can be replaced by smaller amount of magnetically targeted drug. Magnetic carriers receive magnetic responses to a magnetic field from incorporated materials that are used for magnetic microspheres are chitosan, dextran etc. The different types are therapeutic magnetic microspheres and diagnostic microspheres [11,12]

A. Therapeutic magnetic microspheres

It is used to deliver chemotherapeutic agent to liver tumor. Drugs like proteins and peptides can also be targeted through this system.

B. Diagnostic microspheres

It can be used for imaging liver metastases and also can be used to distinguish bowel loops from other abdominal structures by forming nano size particles supramagnetic iron oxides.

3. Floating microspheres

In floating types the bulk density is less than the gastric fluid and so remains buoyant in stomach without affecting gastric emptying rate. The drug is released slowly at the desired rate, if the system is floating on gastric content and increases gastric residence and increases fluctuation in plasma concentration. Moreover it also reduces chances of striking and dose dumping. One another way it produces prolonged therapeutic effect and therefore reduces dosing frequencies. [13]

4. Radioactive microspheres

Radioimmobilization therapy microspheres sized 10-30 nm is of larger than capillaries and gets trapped in first capillary bed when they come across. They are injected to the arteries that lead to

tumour of interest. So all these conditions radioactive microspheres deliver high radiation dose to the targeted areas without damaging the normal surrounding tissues. It differs from drug delivery system, as radio activity is not released from microspheres but acts from within a radioisotope typical distance and the different kinds of radioactive microspheres are β emitters, α emitters.[14]

5. Polymeric microspheres

The different types of polymeric microspheres can be classified as follows and they are biodegradable polymeric microspheres and synthetic polymeric microspheres.[15]

ADVANTAGES

Reliable means delivering the medicine to the target location with specificity, if changed, and maintaining the desired concentration at the place of interest without causing adverse effects. Solid biodegradable microspheres have the ability to deliver drugs in a regulated manner throughout their matrix.

Microspheres have attracted a lot of interest for not just their long-term release, but also their ability to target anticancer medications to tumors. The size, surface charge, and surface hydrophilicity of microspheres have been shown to be essential in influencing particle destiny in vivo.

Studies on macrophage uptake of microspheres have revealed their promise in directing medications to infections that reside intracellularly.

APPLICATIONS OF MICROSPHERES

1. Microspheres in chemotherapy

The most potential use of microspheres is as anti-tumor agent carriers. Microspheres were

administered with increased endocytic activity and leaky vasculature. Soluble polyoxy ethylene is coated to create stealth microspheres. Chemotherapy for cancer may also benefit from the buildup of non-stealth microspheres in the Reticulo Endothelial System (RES).[16, 17]

2. Microspheres for DNA Delivery

Recently, plasmid DNA has been delivered via microspheres, improving both the transfer of plasmid DNA and its stability in the bioenvironment³⁸. Using DNA-gelatin microspheres or nanoparticles created by salt-induced complex coacervation of gelatin and plasmid DNA, Truong-Le & Co. (1998) created a unique gene delivery technique.

3. Fluorescent microspheres

These are composed of polystyrene or poly vinyl toluene, with a monodisperse system spanning in size from 20nm to 4 μ m. Preparation of fluorescent microspheres involves expanding the polymeric microsphere so that fluorescent dyes can enter the microsphere pores. Unswelling the polymeric microspheres causes the fluorescent dyes to get physically entrapped in the pores.[18]

5. Adjuvant effect for vaccines

Several investigations on liquid or oral administration have shown that microspheres/nanoparticles can act as an adjuvant with either matrix-entrapped or surface adsorbed vaccines. "Kreuter & Co-workers" found that polymethyl methacrylate microspheres bearing the influenza antigen elicited a substantial antibody response. Oral administration of antigens via microspheres may be an elegant way to boost Immunoglobulin A (Ig A) antibody response.

6. Microspheres for Ocular delivery

The majority of medication loaded ocular delivery devices are used for glaucoma treatment, particularly cholinergic agonists like as pilocarpine. The low elimination half life of aqueous eye drops can be extended from a very short time (1-3 min) to a longer duration (15-20 min) utilizing microspheres with biodegradable qualities, such as polyalkyl cyanoacrylate.[19]

7. Microspheres for Lymph targeting

The primary goal of lymph targeting is to give effective anticancer chemotherapy that prevents tumor cell metastasis by accumulating the drug in the localized lymph node. Examples include polyalkyl cyanoacrylate microspheres containing anticancer medicines for peritoneal cavity tumors. Poly (lactide-co-glycolide) microspheres are used to provide diagnostic chemicals through the lymphatic system.[19]

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29. DESIGN AND EVALUATION OF MICROSPHERES: A REVIEW Chitra Singh¹, Suresh Purohit², Madhu Singh³, B.L.Pandey⁴ 1. Ph.D scholar, Department of pharmacology, BHU, Varanasi 2. Associate professor, Department of pharmacology, BHU, Varanasi.

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